

**PEDAGOGICAL THOUGHTS ON EDUCATION IN RUSSIA AT THE
END OF THE 19th - EARLY 20th CENTURY**

Ismailov Tokhirjon Khushnubek ugli

researcher

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Abstract: Research shows that the level of patriotism among schoolchildren is significantly decreasing. There is a westernization of consciousness, a change in value paradigms, and this does not contribute to the integration of society. The problem of dominance of one or another accent in issues of patriotic education occupies the modern discursive field of pedagogical thought: freedom, individual rights, the priority of educating citizens or superiority over individual structures - state, society, nation as factors of social integration? Pedagogical ideas of the late 19th and early 20th centuries allow us to see the main aspects of the problem.

Key words: history of pedagogical thought, education, citizenship, civic education and upbringing.

Introduction.

In the conditions of democratization of public life, the principle of openness of education acquires new directions: the aspects of child's personality education related to the perception of the surrounding world as a global space are relevant. At the same time, the perception of the world as an open space causes an ambiguous reaction in the receiver: the westernization of consciousness, which occurs in the conditions of modern culture, leads to the development of patterns of the "western" pattern, the development of the "western" way of life, and at the same time It helps to reduce the role of people z in the socio-historical process. Recent studies show that schoolchildren are less and less interested in connecting their destiny with their country, preferring to use any opportunity to go abroad - both for income and for living.

Undoubtedly, in this regard, modern forms and methods of open education require correction, because they do not contribute to the full growth of the sense of patriotism among children and adolescents. The role of freedom in the upbringing of school-aged children should not simultaneously dominate the role of their obligations as citizens of the Motherland, but this happens with modern students. "Each generation can have its own ideals - mine has its ideals, yours has others, and a generation that has none is a pity," wrote V. Klyuchevsky¹.

¹ Klyuchevsky V.O. Op. in 9 volumes. Course of Russian history. Part 1. M.: Mysl, 1987. T. I. 430 p.

In recent years, the field of informational speech dedicated to the importance and role of educating young students in the spirit of citizenship and patriotism in public pedagogical speech is growing. Issues of interrelationship of the role of Western and national values, including patriotic values, occupy a leading place in the works of local teachers - both classics and moderns. Undoubtedly, the relevance of these issues continues to this day.

We can say that in the conditions of large-scale socio-cultural changes, there is a need to create a civic-patriotic education system based on the achievements of foreign and local pedagogical experience, taking into account national characteristics. Local teacher I. A. Ilyin (1883-1954) believed that education should begin with the development of the emotional sphere, and prioritized the need to refer to the national spiritual experience, because he believed that without this experience, "a spiritual personality can be formed not" he considered².

In the 19th century, revolutionary pedagogy aimed at educating a person in the spirit of freedom and justice is actively developing, its goal is to change the existing order of things, to overthrow autocracy, to deny oneself for the benefit of the people and the state. This direction is in the revolutionary and pedagogical heritage of A. N. Radishchev, the Decembrists, V. G. Belinsky, N. A. Dobrolyubov, A. I. Hertsen, N. G. Chernyshevsky. In the works of these scientists, issues of social and national relations occupy the main place in the education of the individual, its effective, subjective beginning is emphasized. Thus, V. G. Belinsky (1811-1848) believed that love for the Motherland should be effective, the patriotism of a person is manifested in his willingness to give his life for the benefit of the people and the Motherland³.

N. A. Dobrolyubov (1836-1861) introduces the concept of "civic heroism" and for him, patriotism lies in the individual's willingness and ability to rebel against social injustice⁴.

According to A. I. Hertsen (1812-1870), the goal of educating a person is "to go to life, to serve humanity; it is necessary to educate people who know their homeland, customs, traditions, language"⁵.

As you can see, the pedagogical ideas of the revolutionary democrats were to fight for justice, to educate the people through the Will to great, heroic actions

² Ilyin I.A. Our tasks / Collection. Op.: In 10 volumes. T. 2. Book. 1. M., 1993.

³ Belinsky V.G. Full collection Op. in 13 volumes. Editorial coll. R.F. Belchikov et al. M, 1954. T.4.

⁴ Dobrolyubov N.A. Favorite ped. Op. - M., 1986.

⁵ Chronicle of the life and work of A.I. Herzen 1859-June 1864. M., 1983.

that bring freedom to the people, and to educate the individual in the spirit of patriotism and service to the Motherland.

In contrast to the revolutionary democrats, the pedagogical direction of Slavophilism presented in the views of K. S. Aksakov, I. V. Kireevsky, A. S. Khomyakov means the formation of a citizen who is a carrier of national spirituality based on religious principles. For example, A. S. Khomyakov (1804-1860) believed that nationality and religiosity are the basis of education and upbringing of a person.

N. I. Pirogov (1810-1881) sees the development of a sense of patriotism in him as the main task of educating and training a human citizen. K. D. Ushinsky (1824-1871) believed that the "principle of the nation" is the basis of personality education, as a result of which the individuality of each nation is preserved and passes from generation to generation, forming national spirituality.

At the beginning of the 20th century. the issue of the vector of patriotic education of the individual appeared with new force due to the importance of Western "pessimistic theories" (A. Schopenhauer, F. Nietzsche, X. Ortega-I-Gasset) and their influence on the development of spirituality.

Thus, at the beginning of the XIX-XX centuries, in socio-philosophical and pedagogical thoughts, the image of patriotism and the foundations of its upbringing in the young generation are formed, firstly, through the primacy of the spiritual principle over the material, and secondly, the social principle over the individual. This is evident in the views of scientists, both revolutionary-democratic and national-religious thinkers. At the same time, he saw national priorities as opposed to nationalism; unlike the cosmopolitan, the basis of education of the nation and the individual is patriotism, citizenship, community, and spirituality.

According to philosophers and teachers of the analyzed period, the school should be a "living" entity that educates students in the spirit of patriotism. This idea is clearly observed, for example, in the works of P. F. Kapterev, V. V. Rozanov, I. A. Ilyin, and S. I. Hessen. At the same time, along with the direction in foreign and local pedagogy that gives priority to the state and the country, a parallel direction is also developing that focuses on the individual as a subject and educates him in the spirit of freedom⁶.

The general meaning of education is to form a person who will harmoniously enter the society. Education is a process of purposeful influence

⁶ Ilyin I.A. Our tasks / Collection. Op.: In 10 volumes. T. 2. Book. 1. M., 1993.

on a person to form certain values, principles and models of behavior, evaluation systems, attitudes towards oneself, others, the world, and society.

Summarizing the ideas of these scientists, we can come to the conclusion that citizenship and patriotism are related concepts aimed at public service, self-awareness for the state and society with the general goal and idea of educating a person. At the same time, the concept of "citizenship" emphasizes his individual, personal principle in a person more, because it refers not only to the definition of obligations, but also to his rights and freedoms as a citizen. In foreign public opinion, citizenship education and upbringing issues are given priority, and in local pedagogical practice, this concept is still being tested.

When using the concept of "civic education" in local pedagogy, it is often necessary to talk about identifying it with the concept of "civic-patriotic education". In this case, two areas of education are combined into a single integrated concept, but in this case there is no clear interpretation of this concept in local pedagogical practice. With this approach, the formation of citizenship and patriotism should be understood as a comprehensive description of personality development, and civic-patriotic education should be understood as a system with a complex of elements (*educational directions*).

Perhaps this is the most reasonable interpretation that can be given in distinguishing and combining the terms under consideration. Education of students in the spirit of freedom, focusing on knowledge of their rights and obligations as a factor of individualization of the individual in society, in our opinion, should be harmoniously supplemented with education in the spirit of belonging and loyalty of the individual to his Motherland, society, people. In this regard, the pedagogical heritage of foreign and domestic scientists and thinkers can greatly help in the formation of a single correct, logically constructed and practically proven methodology for educating schoolchildren in the spirit of patriotism.

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